

FORENSIC ACCOUNTING SKILLS AND FRAUD CONTROL IN GOVERNMENT MINISTRIES IN AKWA IBOM STATE

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Abstract

This study aimed at determining the extent of utilisation of forensic accounting skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. Descriptive survey research design was used as a design in this study. The target population of the study was 1230 accounting officers from the 20 government ministries in Akwa Ibom State. The sample size for the study was 302 accounting officers in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. A researcher developed instrument known as “Forensic Accounting Skills and Fraud Control Questionnaire” (FASFCQ) which was used for data collection. The instrument was face-validated by three research experts, two from Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. A pilot test of the instrument was carried out using 60 accounting officers who were not part in the actual study. Thereafter, the internal consistency of the instrument was determined by using Cronbach’s Alpha statistical tool. The administration of the instrument was carried out by the researcher with the help of at least one research assistant in each Ministry. Simple linear regression was used in answering the eight research questions as well as testing all the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance. It was found that the utilization of auditing skills, taxation skills and ICT skills helped in fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. Based on the findings and conclusion drawn in this study, it was recommended among others that the government of Akwa Ibom State could develop more interest in forensic accounting for monitoring and investigating suspected culprits in fraud cases.

Keywords: Forensic Accounting, Fraud, Auditing Skills, Linear Regression, FASFCQ.

1 Introduction

Fraud is a severe problem which affects organisations globally and is a major concern in developing nations. Fraud is so endemic and is gradually becoming a normal way of life in both public and private sectors; from the presidential cabinets, down to the political officers, to the ward councillors, from managing directors of companies, through middle management cadre and to lower managers. Individuals perpetrate fraud according to the capacity of their offices. Fraud affects the whole world, however, the magnitude of fraud in Nigeria and the extent to which the economy is affected is very alarming (Abiola, 2019).

Fraud has been associated with human organisation from recorded history. It is an act of deception intended for personal gain or to cause a loss to another party, the eradication of which has remained elusive in most parts of human society. Seetharaman, Sentivelmurugan and Periyannagam (2014) observed that the characteristics of perpetrators showed that the fraud influencing factors include age, gender, position, educational background and existence of motive for collusion. The growth of digital computer technology procreates fraud and generates additional risks of swindling the illicit activities. The widespread of frauds in modern organisations have made traditional auditing and investigation inefficient and ineffective in the detection and prevention of the various types of frauds confronting organisations and businesses world-wide (Onuora and Appah, 2012). The incidence of fraud continues to increase across public and private sector organisations and across nations.

The Nigerian society is filled with stories of wrong practices such as stories of ghost workers on the pay roll of Ministries, Extra-ministerial Departments and Parastatals, frauds, embezzlements and setting ablaze of offices housing sensitive documents and corruption is found everywhere in the country (Okwoli, 2014). According to Bello (2011), huge amount of Naira is lost through one financial malpractice or the other in Nigeria, which drains the nation's meager resources through fraudulent means with far-reaching and attendant consequences on the development of socio-economic or political programmes of the nation. Billions of Naira is lost in the public sector every year through fraudulent means. This represents only the amount that is ferreted out and made public. Indeed, much more substantial or huge sums are lost in undetected frauds. Appah and Appiah (2010) argued that cases of fraud are

prevalent in the Nigerian public sector that every segment of the public service, could seem to be involved in one way or the other in some of these nasty acts.

Today, modern organised financial crimes have appeared. Financial crimes such as employee's theft, payroll frauds, fraudulent billing systems, management theft, corporate frauds, insurance fraud, embezzlement, bribery, bankruptcy, security fraud, among others, have taken the centre stage in the scheme of things; and on the scale of private, public and governmental preference (Economic and Financial Crime Commission [EFCC], 2014). The huge loss due to fraud in the public sector environment has a direct impact on the development of infrastructure, facilities, utilities, and building the public trust. It behoves management in any government ministry, department, and agencies to design procedures primarily meant to detect and prevent fraud from internal and external activities that may be difficult for any fraud perpetrator to penetrate. No country is immune to fraud, since it can come in several ways, either through internal or external connivance.

The growing level of fraud in Nigeria and the world at large makes the need for use of forensic accounting in fraud investigation very apt. There has been offensive increase in financial fraud in the corporate world and Government agencies in Nigeria. The politicians, the bank directors/executives, the legal officers to the law enforcement personnel, the civil servants to the school teacher, the trader in the market to the hawkers on the street, the tendency for fraud and fraud related crimes is endless (Mukoro, Yamusa and Faboyede 2013). This has increased the need for forensic accounting services to detect and prevent the continuous perpetuation of fraud. The detection and prevention of fraud may be effectively achieved with adequate application of forensic accounting.

Owojori and Asaolu (2019) saw forensic accounting as the integration of accounting, auditing and investigative skills to obtain a desired result. Rassey (2019) viewed forensic accounting as the "use of accounting principles and investigative techniques to ferret out fraud and theft". Ramaswamy (2017) viewed forensic accounting as accounting analysis that can uncover possible frauds that are suitable for presentation in court. Ramaswamy maintained that such analysis will form the basis for discussion, debate and dispute resolution. Forensic accounting includes the use of accounting auditing and investigative

skills to assist in legal matters (Okoye and Gbengi, 2013).

Auditing skill is one of the skills required of forensic accountants to checkmate fraud. Auditing skill is a management technique that has been recognized to provide management with a general situation regarding resources utilization and other services within the organization (Botha and Boon, 2013). Akpata (2011) defined auditing skill as a skill that is used to carry out independent examination of accounting records with a view to ascertaining their accuracy and their compliance with relevant rules and regulations as well as with the organizational policies and procedures. Crumbley (2013) defined auditing skill in relation to forensic accounting as an accounting analysis that can uncover possible fraud that is suitable for presentation in court. A forensic accountant uses his knowledge of accounting, law, investigative auditing, criminology, and psychology to uncover fraud, find evidences and present such evidences in court if required. Hence, utilisation of auditing skills can aid in discovery of tax fraud and effective tax system.

Taxation skill is required by accounting officers to checkmate tax evasion and tax avoidance. Tax fraud involved tax evasion which is the efforts by individuals, firms, trusts and other entities to evade taxes by illegal means and this is very prevalent in Nigeria. Fatoki (2014) argued that tax evasion is a deliberate and willful practice of not disclosing full taxable income in order to pay less tax. It is a deliberate violation of tax laws which is evident in situations where tax liability is fraudulently reduced or false claims are filled on the revenue tax forms (Soyode and Kajola, 2016). Therefore, a forensic accountant is vested with taxation skills to curb tax fraud. An effective application of information and communication technology can aid to curb tax fraud. This in turn, will enhance the introduction and application of ICT to checkmate fraud

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skill is critical in fraud control. Bhasin (2015) remarked that, “technology is like a double-edged sword. On the one hand, perpetrators are using it to further fraudulent schemes; on the other hand, experts are making some of their best progress using the same technology. Undoubtedly, technology can prove helpful in fraud detection and prevention in government ministries. As technology becomes more advanced, fraudulent schemes become more complex, while more sophisticated fraud solutions will be developed to combat hackers’ best

efforts.” Unfortunately, the fraud takes on many forms to be handled with any ‘single’ application or approach. As the landscape of fraud continues to shift, business leaders must be aware of trends and predictions that will allow them to implement internal/external controls and systems to help reduce the risk of fraud and keep them from becoming another statistic (Mueller, 2015). The utilization of ICT would bring serious change and improvement in the method of fraud control. This can also enhance the quality of internal control.

Oboh (2012) observed that forensic accounting has helped to uncover and reduce frauds in countries such as Britain, Canada, Germany and United States of America where it is in use, but no known research has been done in Akwa Ibom State public sector on the use of forensic accounting in checking frauds. It has become pertinent that the forensic accounting skills and techniques could help to investigate fraud occurrence since the external auditors may not have the required training to be able to tackle modern frauds like white collar crimes such as security fraud, embezzlement, bankruptcy, contract disputes, and possible criminal financial transactions; including money laundering by organized criminals. It is against this background that this study seeks to determine the extent of utilisation of forensic accounting skills and fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

Fraud is a universal problem as no nations is resistant, although developing countries and their various states suffer the most excruciating experience. The incidence of fraud continues to increase across private and public sector organizations and across the nations. Today; modern organized frauds have appeared. Fraud such as employee thefts, payroll frauds, fraudulent billing systems, management thefts, corporate frauds, insurance frauds, embezzlement, bribery, bankruptcy, security frauds, among others, have taken the centre stage in the scheme of things; and on the scale of private, public and governmental preference (Economic and Financial Crime Commission, 2004). Financial crimes today have grown wild, and the emergences of computer software coupled with the advent of internet facilities have compounded the problem of financial crimes. Besides, the detection or minimisation of these crimes are made more difficult, and committing these crimes much easier.

Fraudulent practices among Nigerians are major challenges facing the development of the country. In recent times, series of frauds have been

committed both in the public sector and private sector of the economy. The Federal Government has been making several efforts in tackling these dreadful menaces by setting up many anti-corruption institutions to tackle cases of frauds and other activities of financial and economic crimes but the efforts seemed not to have yielded the desired results or have not been effective. No doubt, frauds have affected individuals and corporate organisations negatively. This has put accounting professional bodies into a new perception and paradigm that go beyond statutory audit to employ a more technical approach called “forensic accounting” to curb fraudulent practices in public sectors of the economy. Fraud has become the specialty in public sector in Nigeria as individuals perpetrate frauds according to the capacity of their office. Accordingly, there is a general expectation that forensic accounting may be able to stem the tide of fraud witnessed in public sector of the Nigerian economy. However, there has not been adequate emphasis, especially survey evidences on how forensic accounting can help curtail fraud beyond the several unreliable views that abound.

The spate of corporate failures has placed greater responsibility and functions on accountants to equip themselves with the skills to identify and act upon indicators of fraud. It has become imperative for the accountants at all levels to have the requisite skills and knowledge for identifying, discovering as well as preserving the evidence of all forms of fraud. Therefore, fraud requires more sophisticated approach from preventative to detection. One of the modern approaches that can be used from the prevention to detection is called forensic accounting. In the light of the above, this study therefore seeks to determine the extent to which forensic accounting skills influence fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

The main purpose of this study was to determine the extent of utilization of forensic accounting skills by accounting officers to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. The specific purposes of this study were to determine the extent to which accounting officers utilised:

- i. auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.
- ii. taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.
- iii. Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

The study was guided by the following research questions:

- i. To what extent do accounting officers utilise auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries?
- ii. To what extent do accounting officers utilise taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries?
- iii. To what extent do accounting officers utilise Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries?

The following null hypotheses were formulated to guide the study and tested at .05 level of significance.

Ho₁: Accounting officers do not significantly utilise auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

Ho₂: Accounting officers do not significantly utilize taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

Ho₃: Accounting officers do not significantly utilise Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

2 Methodology

Descriptive survey research design was used in this study. The population of the study was 1230 accounting officers in Akwa Ibom State Ministries (Office of the Accountant General, Akwa Ibom State, 2018). The sample size for the study was 302 accounting officers in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. It was statistically determined using Taro Yamane formula. Cluster sampling technique was used for the study. A researcher developed instrument known as “Forensic Accounting Skills and Fraud Control Questionnaire” (FASFCQ) which was used for data collection. The instrument was divided into three sections: Section A sought to elicit general information on the personal data of the respondents such as their ministry and sex. Section B contained 30 items on Forensic Accounting Skills which were grouped into three major categories namely; auditing skills, taxation skills and ICT skills. Each has ten items. Section C contains 20 items on fraud control. Respondents were required to indicate the extent to which they utilise each of the listed forensic skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. The questionnaire was structured on a 4-point rating scale with options ranging as; Very Highly Utilised (4 points), Highly Utilised (3 points), Lowly Utilised (2 points) and Very Lowly Utilised (1 point). The instrument was face-validated by three research experts,

two from the Faculty of Education, University of Uyo. A trial test of the instrument was carried out using 60 accounting officers who did not take part in the actual study. Thereafter, the internal consistency of the instrument was determined using Cronbach’s Alpha statistical tool. The reliability coefficients were; auditing skills = .83, taxation skills = .75 and ICT skills = .73. The overall total of the co-efficient index was .77. The simple linear regression statistics was used to provide answers to the research questions and to test the null hypotheses at .05 level of significance.

3 RESULTS

Research Question 1

To what extent do accounting officers utilise auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries?

Table 1: R and R² of the extent to which Accounting Officer Utilised Auditing Skills to Fraud Control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries

Variables	R	R-square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error
Auditing skills				
Fraud Control	.319	.102	.099	4.447

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The result presented in Table 1 reveals a correlated coefficient R-value of .319 which shows that auditing skills was highly utilised by accounting officers to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. The table further showed the coefficient of determination (R²) value as .102. The (R²) value of .102 which is the strength of association implies that 10.2 percent of fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries is attributed to the utilisation of accounting officers’ auditing skills.

Research Question 2

To what extent do accounting officers utilise taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries?

Table 2: R and R² of the extent to which Accounting Officers Utilised Taxation Skills to Control Fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries

Variables	R	R-square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error
Taxation Practices	.509	.259	.256	4.039
Fraud Control				

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The result presented in Table 4.2 reveals a correlated coefficient R-value of .509 which shows that taxation skills was very highly utilised by accounting officers to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. The table further showed the coefficient of determination (R²) value as .259. This implies that the extent of fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries is attributed to 25.9 percent of the utilization of taxation skills by accounting officers.

Research Question 3

To what extent do accounting officers utilise Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries?

Table 3: R and R² of the extent to which ICT Skills of Accounting Officers Influence Fraud Control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries

Variables	R	R-square	Adjusted R-square	Std. Error
ICT Skills	.601	.361	.359	3.751
Fraud Control				

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The result presented in Table 3 reveals a correlated coefficient R-value of .319 which shows that ICT skills was very highly utilised by accounting officers to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. The table further showed the coefficient of determination (R²) value as .361. This implies that the extent of fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries is attributed to 36.1 percent of the utilization of ICT skills by accounting officers.

H₀₁: Accounting officers do not significantly utilise auditing skills to control

fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

Table 4: Result of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the Auditing Skills Utilised by Accounting Officers to Control Fraud Akwa Ibom State Ministries (n = 290)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	P-Value	Remarks
Regression	646.498	1	646.498	32.697**	.000	
Residual	5694.481	288	19.773			
Total	6340.979	289				

**significant at P= .05

Source: Field Survey, 2019.

The result in Table 4 shows that the computed F-value as 32.697 with 1 and 288 degrees of freedom as well as the p-value of .000. Since the p-value is less than ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis which states that accounting officers do not significantly utilised auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries is rejected, while the alternative is retained. Hence, it was concluded that accounting officers significantly utilised auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

HO₂: Accounting officers do not significantly utilise taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

Table 5: Result of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the Taxation Skills Utilised by Accounting Officers to Control Fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries (n = 290)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	P- Value	Remarks
Regression	1642.122	1	1642.122	100.648**	.000	
Residual	4698.858	288	16.315			
Total	6340.979	289				

**significant at P= .05; Source: Field Survey, 2019

The result in Table 5 shows that the computed F-value as 100.648 with 1 and 288 degrees of freedom as well as the p-value of .000. Since the p-value is less than ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis which states that accounting officers do not significantly utilised taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries is rejected, while the alternative is retained. It can therefore be

concluded that accounting officers do significantly utilized forensic taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

HO₃: Accounting officers do not significantly utilise Information and Communication Technology (ICT) skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

Table 6: Result of Simple Linear Regression Analysis of the ICT skills Utilised by Accounting Officers to Control Fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries (n = 290)

Model	Sum of Squares	Df	Mean Square	F-cal	P- Value	Remarks
Regression	2288.440	1	2288.440	162.632**	.000	Sig
Residual	4052.539	288	14.071			
Total	6340.979	289				

**significant at P= .05

Source: Field Survey, 2019

The result in Table 6 shows that the computed F-value as 162.632 with 1 and 288 degrees of freedom as well as the p-value of .000. Since the p-value is less than ($p < .05$), the null hypothesis which states that accounting officers do not significantly utilised ICT skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries is rejected, while the alternative is retained. It can therefore be concluded that accounting officers do significantly utilise ICT skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

1 Discussion of Findings

The finding of research question one revealed that auditing skill was highly utilised by accounting officers control fraud in Akwa Ibom Ministries. The hypothesis one indicated that accounting officers significantly utilised auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. This necessitates the rejection of the null hypothesis and the retention of the alternate hypothesis. This positive result could be as a result of training and retraining of accounting officers in Accounting Technical Scheme (ATS), Institute of Chartered Accountants of Nigeria (ICAN), Association of National Accountants of Nigeria (ANAN) and other professional bodies which stand as a criterion for their promotion.

The finding is in line with the view of Albretch and Albretch (2011) who

described forensic auditing as the utilisation of specialised investigative skills in carrying out an enquiry conducted in such a manner that the outcome will have application to the court of law. The authors further stated that the primary aim of forensic auditing is fraud detection, unlike the traditional auditing that focuses on review of internal control system, error identification and prevention. Forensic auditors are experienced auditors, accountants, and investigators of legal and financial documents that are hired to look into possible suspicion of fraudulent activity within an organization or a company; or are hired by a company who may just want to prevent fraudulent activities from occurring (Albretch and Albretch, 2011).

The finding of research question two revealed that taxation skill was very highly utilised by accounting officers control fraud in Akwa Ibom Ministries. The hypothesis one indicated that accounting officers significantly utilised taxation skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. This necessitates the rejection of the null hypothesis and the retention of the alternate hypothesis. This positive result could be as a result of training and retraining of accounting officers in accounting officers in professional institutions relating to taxation and workshops and conferences organize for them annually.

The findings of this study agreed with Al-Sharaivi (2018) and Modugu and Anyaduba (2013) who revealed that forensic accounting is perceived to have evolved in response to certain emerging fraud related cases of which tax evasion is inclusive. Okoye and Gbegi (2013) also maintained that forensic accounting is a specialized field of accounting that describes engagements that result from actual or anticipated disputes or litigation.

The finding of research question three revealed that auditing skill was highly utilised by accounting officers control fraud in Akwa Ibom Ministries. The hypothesis three indicated that accounting officers significantly utilised auditing skills to control fraud in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. This necessitates the rejection of the null hypothesis and the retention of the alternate hypothesis. This positive result could be as a result of training and retraining of accounting officers in ICT packages to handle fraud, forensic software, Accounting Technical Scheme (ATS) and other professional bodies.

This positive result could also be attributed to the recruited of consultants in ICT and accounting in different ministries and also the compulsory training of staff in ICT.

The findings is in consonance with the view of Bagga and Singh (2011) who reported that forensic analytics software is mostly use to control fraud in public and private domain. Some of the software are namely; Audit Command Language (ACL), Interactive Data Extraction and Analysis (IDEA), Statistical Analysis System (SAS), and Microsoft Data Analyser. The ACL can be used as audit data analytics, monitoring and auditing of the company, investigating and detecting fraudulent activities certifying compliance within company policies and developing secure data access for all users (Aiken, 2016). The ACL gathers valuable information for decision-making purposes. The data will be checked manually to confirm whether all the required and adequate fields are provided or not. After confirming that the data are successfully imported into the ACL tool, the raw data will then be processed (Wadhawan and Mahajan, 2016).

5 CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

5.1 Conclusion

The following conclusions were drawn based on the findings of this study on ‘forensic accounting skills and fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries. On the basis of this study it can be deduced that there is a significant influence of auditing skills, taxation skills and ICT skills influence fraud control in Akwa Ibom State Ministries.

The role of a forensic accountant under contemporary conditions no doubt is very important because they help professional and regulatory bodies and other institutions in investigating and documenting frauds. The increasing occurrence of fraud in modern day ministries and business environment require the services of forensic accountants to unearth fraudulent activities within and outside an organization. The continued audit failures over decades have prompted a paradigm shift in accounting. It is generally accepted that an auditor has the duty to perform tests to detect material defalcation and errors if they exist. However, fraud detection experts called forensic accountants are now being hired in developed economies to investigate cases of fraud. It is concluded that forensic accounting plays some significant roles in the

controlling of fraud, financial crimes and corruption in organisations.

5.2 Recommendations

Based on the findings and conclusion of this study, the following are recommended:

- i. Government of Akwa Ibom State could develop more interest in forensic accounting for monitoring and investigating suspected culprits in fraud cases.
- ii. Directors and permanent secretaries promoted and appointed in different ministries should be tested and the integrity and trustworthiness could be proven before they are appointed to oversee the affairs in different ministries.
- iii. Financial laws could be up to date with latest advancement in technology to ensure admissibility of evidence in a law court for successful prosecution of criminal cases.

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